

USE OF DRONES IN E COMMERCE

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ABSTRACT

The use of drones in last mile logistics for deliveries has gained increasing popularity in recent years. This paper examines the advantages and limitations associated with drone deliveries and addresses the question of whether drones are the future of last mile logistics. It highlights the factors that need to be resolved or considered before drone delivery can become mainstream. Additionally, this paper investigates the environmental impact of drone deliveries, specifically focusing on the amount of CO₂ emissions saved compared to other types of deliveries. By analyzing existing research and industry insights, this paper provides a comprehensive understanding of the potential of drones in last mile logistics and the challenges that need to be addressed for their widespread adoption.

INTRODUCTION

Delivery companies are actively seeking innovative solutions to enhance their last mile delivery operations. While some companies still rely on traditional vans, others have made the switch to using drones. However, despite the advanced capabilities of modern-day drones, they also have certain limitations. Airspace restrictions and limited range are among the primary challenges. Considering this, it is crucial to question whether vans, with their higher CO₂ emissions and slower delivery times, truly offer a better alternative. This article highlights the advantages and limitations of drones in the current landscape, allowing readers to assess for themselves whether drones are the future of last mile logistics. This article aims to address the following research questions:

To what extent are drone deliveries expected to increase?

How much can CO₂ emissions be reduced through the use of drone deliveries?

Are drone deliveries faster than traditional delivery vans?

Through comprehensive analysis, this article provides insights into these research questions, enabling readers to make informed judgments about the potential of drones in shaping the future of last mile logistics.

NINE WAYS DRONES ARE ALREADY USED IN BUSINESS

Drones are everywhere. Since taking the business world by storm in late 2016, the technology has quickly transformed from a nice-to-have luxury, into a must-have commodity. Like with any new technology, some people embrace the modernization, while some are hesitant to change the way that things have been done for years. Although the drone industry is still relatively new, drones have yet to reach their full potential, but their impact has not been small. Drones provide a cost effective, safe, and accessible way to take aerial photos and video, gather and analyze data, deliver goods, observe inaccessible areas, and so much more (Shore, 2022):

1. Drone Photography
2. Disaster Relief
3. Real Estate Marketing
4. Safety inspections
5. Drone Delivery
6. Data Gathering, Surveying, Mapping, Monitoring
7. Advancements in Artificial Intelligence
8. Safety Issues and Government Regulation
9. Monitoring Construction Progress

BENEFITS OF DRONE DELIVERIES

The use of drones for last-mile deliveries—which refers to the final step of the delivery process where the parcel arrives at the customer’s doorstep—may be an effective tool to reduce carbon emissions related to transportation. According to a study by Cell Patterns, using [quadcopter drones](#) to deliver small, lightweight packages could reduce energy consumption and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by up to 94 and 84 percent, respectively, per package delivered. To determine the energy consumption of a small drone, the authors developed an energy model based on 188 drone-delivery flights and found that it consumes approximately 0.08 megajoules of energy per kilometer. Afterward, they compared it to the energy consumption and associated carbon emissions of different delivery vehicles. Based on the study’s findings, only the electric cargo bicycles had a similar or lower carbon footprint per package than the small quadcopter drones. study shows that drones could considerably reduce the energy consumption and GHG emissions of last-mile delivery, helping to mitigate the environmental footprint of the transportation sector. ([Rodrigues](#), 2022)

Table 1: Base-case energy consumption and GHG emissions for different vehicles

Vehicle class	Energy consumption (MJ/km)	Fuel GHG emissions (g/km)	Upstream GHG emissions (g/km)	Battery GHG emissions (g/km)	Energy consumption (MJ/package)	GHG emission (g/package)
Medium-duty diesel truck	11.00	762.8	168.7	–	5.24	443.6
Small diesel van	4.90	339.8	75.2	–	1.41	119.2
Medium-duty electric truck	3.80	674.3	83.7	24.5	1.81	372.6
Small electric van	1.65	293.0	36.4	14.1	0.47	98.7
Electric cargo bicycle	0.10	17.9	2.2	3.3	0.10	23.4
Small quadcopter drone	0.08	14.4	1.8	1.3	0.33	70.1

Source: [Drone flight data reveal energy and greenhouse gas emissions savings for very small package delivery](#)

From table 1 we can find small quadcopter drones and electric cargo bicycles consume considerably less energy than small electric vans and immensely less than medium duty electric trucks, small diesel vans and medium-duty diesel trucks. Which makes them very intriguing for environmentally Friendly & Sustainable Companies

Using energy-efficient vehicles is an important first step for businesses that intend to reduce the carbon emissions of their deliveries, in addition to finding routes where more packages are delivered per mile. Earlier this year, the US Postal Service announced that it placed an order for 50,000 Next Generation Delivery Vehicles to replace its fleet of aging delivery trucks. They intended to purchase at least 10,019 battery electric vehicles (BEV), but after facing several lawsuits for their plan to buy mostly gas-powered delivery vehicles, they increased the number of BEVs to 25,000. Drones can produce even fewer carbon emissions if charged using renewable resources, says Sarah Lyon-Hill, associate director for research development at Virginia Tech Center for Economic and Community Engagement who was not involved in the study. Over time, the carbon emissions of electricity-powered vehicles, drones, vans, trucks, and cargo bicycles are expected to improve as the electricity grid continues to get cleaner. And we'll still need trucks and vans for our bigger deliveries, so greening our electricity use is still crucial. (Rodrigues, 2022)

Figure 1 Graphic representation of energy consumption and CO2 emissions

Source: [Drone flight data reveal energy and greenhouse gas emissions savings for very small package delivery](#)

Figure 1 shows CO2 Emissions produced by different vehicles per package.

CONSUMERS BENEFIT FROM DRONE DELIVERIES

Our transportation infrastructure is currently strained due to the high demand for delivery services, which increased exponentially during the COVID-19 pandemic, says Lyon-Hill. However, even before COVID, plenty of households with needs for home delivery, such as those with elderly residents or lower-income households without car access, had limited transportation options.

“Delivery drones have the potential to address this higher level of demand, decrease road congestion, speed up last-mile delivery services, and offer those services at lower costs to support lower-income households,” says Lyon-Hill. By reducing the number of vans on the road, drone deliveries can [reduce](#) traffic congestion, noise pollution, and harmful emissions.

Companies are already on top of it. Amazon Prime Air, which plans to start drone deliveries this year, is [currently working](#) with the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) and local officials in Lockeford, California to give consumers the option to have their parcels delivered via drones. “Other companies will likely follow this trend” says Rodrigues, “if we develop the conditions to overcome some of the operational and regulatory challenges mentioned.”

Of course, just like with driverless cars and other forms of automation, there are always concerns with what will happen for delivery workers and their jobs. But drone deliveries, even when all of the policy kinks are straightened out, will still only be [one part of future deliveries](#). Until then, making [sustainable choices like ordering fewer times in larger quantities or accepting slower delivery times](#), can help bring down your online shopping footprint no matter how it is delivered. (Delgado, 2022)

DELIVERY DRONES USED TO DELIVER AED-S

According to [EUROPEAN HEART JOURNAL study](#) published in August 2021 drones with automated external defibrillators (AED) were deployed. The AED was successfully delivered onsite in 92 % of the cases and arrived before the ambulance in 64 % of the cases.

In this prospective clinical trial, three AED-equipped drones were placed within controlled airspace in Sweden, covering approximately 80 000 inhabitants (125 km²). Drones were integrated in the emergency medical services for automated deployment in beyond-visual-line-of-sight flights: consecutive real-life suspected OHCA. Primary outcome was the proportion of successful AED deliveries when drones were dispatched in cases of suspected OHCA. Among secondary outcomes was the proportion of cases where AED drones arrived prior to ambulance and time benefit vs. ambulance. Totally, 14 cases were eligible for dispatch during the study period in which AED drones took off in 12 alerts to suspected OHCA, with a median distance to location of 3.1 km. AED delivery was feasible within 9 min from the location and successful in 11 alerts (92%). AED drones arrived prior to ambulances in 64%, with a median time benefit of 01:52 min average when drone arrived first. In an additional 61 test flights, the AED delivery success rate was 90% .(Automated external defibrillators delivered by drones to patients with suspected out-of-hospital cardiac arrest, 2023)

Figure 2: Drone vs EMS AED deliveries

Source: Automated external defibrillators delivered by drones to patients with suspected out-of-hospital cardiac arrest

ELECTRIC VANS DELIVERIES COMPARED TO DRONE DELIVERIES IN CITIES

Using delivery drones in cities consumes up to TEN TIMES more energy than electric vans because they can only carry one parcel at a time and require frequent back and forth trips. One of the main reasons was that drones require continuous energy while out on a delivery, unlike vans, which can be parked and turned off in strategic locations.

Another factor were crosswinds and headwinds, which can increase the amount of energy required to stay on course or hover in place while waiting to complete a delivery at the destination. The one area where drones might have an advantage over vans was in rural settings where they might be able to travel more direct routes and a van wouldn't have the same advantage of being able to park in one spot and have a delivery driver walk to multiple destinations on foot. 'When evaluating the hypothetical use of delivery drones, attention has frequently only been on whether drones could deliver parcels faster and cheaper,' Kirschstein said. (Thomsen, 2020)

LIMITATIONS OF USING THE DRONS

Carrying capacity of drones vary drastically. Drones are generally categorized into four classes: toy, mini, hobby, and professional drones. Those who are brand new to drones usually prefer a toy drone so that if they crash it, it's not a lot of money out of their pocket to replace it (toy drones are about \$30 on average). However professional drones, the payload increases to as much as 25 pounds or even 500 pounds, which means up to 227 kilograms. (Malcazan, 2022)

TYPES OF DRONES AND THEIR WEIGHT LIMITS

- **Microdrones:**
Microdrones are used for aerial photography and rescue operations. They can lift lightweight objects such as vlogging cameras and search cams that weigh about 4.5-44 pounds (2-20 kgs).
- **Heavy lift drones:**
Heavy lift drones have high payload capacity. They are used to take scenic shots in movies from an elevated view. These drones can lift heavy cameras that are impossible for a man to carry alone.
- **Consumer drones:**
Consumer drones carry smaller weights and can be used to deliver small items. Anything that weighs around half a pound should be good to go.
- **Prosumer drones:**
The prosumer drone is a hybrid between consumer and professional drones. It can carry weights up to 6.5 pounds (3 kgs). Prosumer drones like Prime Air are used to deliver packages door-to-door. They are perfect to carry moderate weights. They use sophisticated systems of technologies for them to deliver packages safely.

They have 4-8 propellers and are guided remotely by a stationed operator. The operator can track the movements of the drone while they are flying. Various drone delivery software uses technologies like 4G and GPS to get real-time flight data of the drones. A thorough location tagging system done by the operator helps in the safe landing and take-off of the drones. (How much weight can a delivery drone carry? 2021)

WHAT FACTORS AFFECT THE CARRYING CAPACITY OF DRONES?

The carrying capacity of a drone is affected by its overall weight, the power of its motor, the propellers, and the capacity of its battery. However, the flight is entirely subject to an environment that's suitable for a drone's performance. (Posea, 2022)

- **TYPE OF DRONE**
Smaller drones aren't typically made to lift any sort of extra weight. So, they have lighter components that simply do the job. Professional drones, on the other hand, are meant to be part of a more purposeful system. To make that happen, they're fitted with more and stronger propellers. These components generate the upward thrust required to lift anything additional to the drone.
- **MOTOR POWER**
The importance of the drone's engine to a flight may seem a bit obvious, but it's also relevant to explaining the payload capacity. A more powerful motor increases the power-to-weight ratio of a drone. This allows it to generate more of a lift and, hence, carry a greater payload. Why not just fit every drone with a powerful motor? Because of weight and battery type.
- **BATTERY**

A motor will only function if it has the right type of battery facilitating it. A drone with a powerful motor consumes more energy and, therefore, needs a battery with a bigger capacity. And a large battery adds to the overall weight, which would only limit the entire system. What's more, an additional payload will not only affect the drone's agility but also reduce the flight time. (Posea, 2022)

Table 2: Top 5 drones by payload (Max)

Drone	Payload (Max)
GRIFF 300	496 lb (225 kg)
FB 4 Transportation Drone	441 lb (200kg)
xFold rigs Dragon X12 U11 Drone	100 lb (45kg)
DJI Agras T20	44 lb (20kg)
DJI Agras MG-1S	22 lb (10kg)

Source: Drone Payloads: Which Drone Can Carry the Most Weight?

Above are 5 examples of professional drones and the maximum weight they can carry according to dronesvue.com. All drones are designed for a specific purpose and are tested with a maximum payload for their use. For example, it's useless for a photography drone to have a high payload since it wouldn't utilize it.

AIR SPACE LIMITATIONS

Different countries have different laws and stances on air space regulations. I provided USA regulations due to the fact that most drone deliveries are currently being done in USA.

USA example: FAA rules apply to the entire National Airspace System – there is no such thing as "unregulated" airspace. Drone operators should be familiar with the difference between controlled and uncontrolled airspace, and where you can legally fly. Controlled airspace is found around some airports and at certain altitudes where air traffic controllers are actively communicating with, directing, and separating all air traffic. Other airspace is considered uncontrolled in the sense that air traffic controllers are not directing air traffic within its limits.

In general, you can only fly your drone in uncontrolled airspace below 400 feet above the ground (AGL). Commercial drone operators are required to get permission from the FAA before flying in controlled airspace. (Airspace 101 – Rules of the Sky, 2023)

Figure 3 Airspace Guidance for small UAS operators

Source: Airspace 101 – Rules of the Sky

WHICH COMPANIES USE DRONE DELIVERY?

Prime Air is one of only three drone-delivery companies that has gone through the rigorous process to earn a FAA air carrier certificate, which will be required to operate drones using these advanced capabilities. It took them years of inventing, testing, and improving to develop these breakthrough technologies, and we're excited to use them to make customer deliveries. (Prime Air prepares for drone deliveries, 2022)

The UAV, or also called drone, is extensively being spread out to various applications and last-mile delivery service is one of the applications which attracts logistics companies including Amazon.com, Inc. Although Amazon Prime Air delivery service using UAVs is widely advertised, slight amount of Amazon delivery UAV information is revealed to public and undermining it became the main purpose of this paper. Throughout the paper, Amazon delivery UAV itself is analysed in the aspect of UAV classification (DoD) and ideal HW specifications: motor, battery pack, controller, and frame. Particularly, the ideal HW specifications of Amazon delivery UAV are deduced by comparing three resources including information from Amazon disclosure, theoretic calculation, and xcopterCalc calculation. (Sunghun, 2017).

Table 3 Ideal Amazon drone

Frame Size(<i>cm</i>)	115
Rotor Size(<i>cm</i>)	43
UAV Weight(<i>kg</i>)	3.8
BLDC Motors	8
Flight Time(<i>min</i>)	30
Top Speed(<i>kph</i>)	80.5
Range(<i>km</i>)	16
Motor RPM(<i>rpm</i>)	10,000
Package Weight(<i>kg</i>)	2.3
Max. Payload(<i>kg</i>)	14
Flight Altitude(<i>m</i>)	< 150(Class G Airspace)
Battery Pack	LiPo 10S, 37 V, 10,000 <i>mAh</i> , 1.7 <i>kg</i>

Source: Analysis of Amazon Prime Air UAV Delivery Service

Table 3 shows the drone technical specifications. Is a Drone-only delivery service primarily focused on food delivery on shorter distances. It operates only on a few locations, since their drones are built to take on 5mile road trips max. Their drones generally fly at 32 mph, enabling them to reach their clients in under five minutes. Drone was implemented in use in 2019. Their drones also have the “heavy-lift” feature. (The food you love, sky delivered in 5 minutes, 2022)

Figure 4: Flytrex drone

Source: Flytrex m600

Figure 4 shows the latest Flytrex drone (the one that is currently in use).

Figure 5: Delivery areas

Source: The food you love, sky delivered in 5 minutes

Figure 5 shows one of the 5 delivery available areas. Their drones deliver to their clients in (Have some questions? 2022):

- Granbury, TX
- Durham, NC
- Holly Springs, NC
- Raeford, NC
- Fayetteville, NC

Wing is a subsidiary of Alphabet Inc. that develops a drone delivery system and UTM systems. The company has operations in Australia, the United States, and Finland. In summary, once a customer submits an order via the Wing mobile app our drone flies to pick up the package at our delivery facility. The drone then climbs to a cruise height on average of about 45 metres (150 feet) above ground, flying to the designated delivery destination in several minutes. Once at the customer destination, the drone slows down, hovers, descends to a delivery height of 7 metres (23 feet) above ground, and then lowers the tether and automatically releases the package in the desired delivery area. There is no need to unclip or assist with the delivery of the package. The drone then climbs back to cruise height and returns to the Wing site. Wing operates somewhat like Wolt or/and Glovo in Slovenia, but with utilisation of drones. (About Delivery 2023)

Figure 6: Wing By the numbers.

Vir: Wing news

By the numbers

300,000

Commercial drone deliveries

2 min 47 seconds

Our fastest delivery

10 locations

Across 3 continents

87%

Approval for drone delivery in our first U.S. service area

Figure 6 shows one of the Wing deliveries being done. Wing also holds the title for one of the world's first ever drone delivery according to Smithsonian Magazine:

The JETSONS-esque dream of on-demand commercial delivery took a step closer on October 18, 2019, when three Wing 7000 delivery drones departed their “nest” established in a Christiansburg, Virginia parking lot. The first to arrive at its destination—after traveling 2.32 miles in two minutes, 50 seconds—was airframe A1229 with delivery of a FedEx-shipped winter vest to Paul and Susie Sensemeier. Like most drones, it was remotely piloted (or more accurately, monitored) by a human. Wing’s control centre has the capability for an operator to control up to 15 drones simultaneously. The National Air and Space Museum has just accepted the donation of A1229 from Wing, one of Alphabet’s companies. (Connor, 2020)

UPS is one of the world’s largest package delivery companies with 2020 revenue of \$84.6 billion and provides a broad range of integrated logistics solutions for customers in more than 220 countries and territories. The company’s more than 540,000 employees embrace a strategy that is simply stated and powerfully executed: Customer First. People Led. Innovation Driven.

UPS claims it takes a strong and unwavering stance in support of diversity, equity, efficiency, and inclusion. “We’re combining simple, elegant design and advanced technology to create a reliable aircraft with zero operational emissions that will revolutionize how cargo moves,” said BETA founder and CEO Kyle Clark. “This is all about innovation with a focus on returns for our business, our customers, and the environment,” said UPS Chief Information and Engineering Officer Juan Perez. “These new aircraft will create operational efficiencies in our business, open possibilities for new services, and serve as a foundation for future solutions to reduce the emissions profile of our air and ground operation. (UPS Flight Forward adds innovative new aircraft, enhancing capabilities and network sustainability, 2021)

DRONE DELIVERY AND LAST-MILE LOGISTICS

Logistics stakeholders are factoring in these benefits, and according to estimates by Fortune Business Insights, this is leading to the global drone package delivery market size to grow from \$1.5 billion in 2021 to an estimated \$31.2 billion by 2028 at a CAGR of 53.94 per cent. (Et contributors, 2022)

Figure 7 Drone usage in transport industry world wide 2021

Share of drone usage in the transportation industry worldwide 2021

Source: (Data from Statista)

Logistics stakeholders are factoring in these benefits, and according to estimates by Fortune Business Insights, this is leading to the global drone package delivery market size to grow from \$1.5 billion in 2021 to an estimated \$31.2 billion by 2028 at a CAGR of 53.94 per cent. Worldwide, e-commerce giants have already started drone deliveries and are looking at penetrating rural and remote areas with drone deliveries. Retailers in the hyperlocal delivery segment are also adopting drones to fulfill last-mile deliveries requests at the least time possible. With use cases of drones in last-mile logistics multiplying daily, industry reports suggest that global drone investments have surged to \$5 billion in the last 10 years with drone manufacturers attracting increasing investments. In India as well, government incentives are encouraging multiple industries, such as healthcare, agriculture, e-commerce and transportation, to experiment with drones. While until now, the use of drones was confined to essential deliveries, the next phase of growth will largely come from their commercial application. Many companies and startups from the e-commerce and food delivery industries are using drones in pilot exercises of middle-mile as well as last-mile deliveries. Ideal for lightweight parcels, drones can deliver a parcel within an estimated round-trip time of 30 minutes. Additionally, as drones are equipped with GPS, customers can track their package in real time and enjoy quick and contactless deliveries. With over 200 startups in the drone sector and conducive policies, the drone and drone component manufacturing industry in India, according to the Ministry of Civil Aviation, is estimated to net an investment of over \$626 million over the next three years. (Et contributors, 2022)

RESEARCH FINDINGS - ANSWERS TO RESEARCH QUESTIONS

To what extent are drone deliveries expected to increase?

According to estimates by Fortune Business Insights, the global drone package delivery market size is to grow from \$1.5 billion in 2021 to an estimated \$31.2 billion by 2028. With use cases of drones in last-mile logistics multiplying daily, industry reports suggest that global drone investments have surged to \$5 billion in the last 10 years with drone manufacturers attracting increasing investments.

How much can CO2 emissions be reduced through the use of drone deliveries?

According to a study by Cell Patterns, using [quadcopter drones](#) to deliver small, lightweight packages could reduce energy consumption and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by up to 94 and 84 percent, respectively, per package delivered.

That being said article published by Michel Thomsen claims that delivery drones in cities consumes up to TEN TIMES more energy than electric vans because they can only carry one parcel at a time and require frequent back and forth trips. Making them less efficient in urban areas in terms of CO2 emissions.

Are drone deliveries faster than traditional delivery vans?

In research: “Delivery drones used to deliver aed-s” made by: European Heart Journal. AED drones arrived prior to ambulances in 64%, with a median time benefit of 01:52 min average when drone arrived first. In an additional 61 test flights, the AED delivery success rate was 90% (55/61). Meaning The AED was successfully delivered onsite in 92 % of the cases and arrived before the ambulance in 64 % of the cases.

CONCLUSION

Drone deliveries have proven to be instrumental for last-mile delivery, with an increasing number of deliveries being carried out by drones instead of traditional delivery vans. The advantages of lower transportation costs and shorter delivery times are driving the adoption of drones in e-commerce. However, there are still challenges to overcome, such as the limited range of flight and aerospace limitations. The carrying capacity of drones varies depending on their classification, with toy drones being suitable for beginners and heavy lift drones designed for professional use. The global drone package delivery market is expected to experience significant growth, with estimates projecting a market size of around \$31.2 billion by 2028. Major players in the e-commerce industry have already embraced drone deliveries and are expanding their operations to reach rural and remote areas. The use cases for drones in last-mile logistics are expanding rapidly, leading to increased investments in the drone industry. Government incentives in countries like India are encouraging various industries to explore drone applications. The commercial application of drones is expected to see significant growth, with companies and startups

conducting pilot exercises for middle-mile and last-mile deliveries. Drones offer quick and contactless deliveries, with real-time package tracking using GPS technology. However, it's important to consider the energy consumption and CO2 emissions associated with drone deliveries, especially in urban areas where they may be less efficient compared to electric vans. Overall, drones have the potential to revolutionize the delivery industry and offer numerous benefits, but there are still challenges and considerations to address in their widespread implementation.

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